

STAR*track
A Built4People Project

Printed version of the “Building as a Lab” (B-a-a-L) web-based guidelines

**A Guide to Testing Innovative Envelope
Solutions in Real Buildings**

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Building as a Lab:

A Guide to Testing Innovative Envelope Solutions in Real Buildings

Measuring the performance of innovative façades and envelope products is crucial before their market launch. Manufacturers need to test and validate their products, ensuring they meet the required standards and expected performance. However, traditional building product testing occurs in controlled laboratory environments, which **fails to capture the complex, dynamic conditions of a real-world environment.**

This creates a **gap between laboratory results and actual field performance**, leading to disappointing outcomes, failed innovations, leading to reluctance in adopting new technologies.

The problem, in a nutshell: **building owners face uncertainties about product performance, while manufacturers struggle to validate their innovations under authentic conditions.**

The solution: Building as a Lab

The 'Building as a Lab' approach transforms occupied buildings into open-innovation test beds.

This method measures the performance of innovative façades and envelope products in real-world conditions. It creates controlled yet **authentic testing environments** within functioning structures, allowing products to be evaluated with real occupants, actual weather patterns, and typical building operations. This approach is **great both for product developers and building owners** by **allowing the validation and improvement of products before their market launch.**

The process involves various stakeholders including building owners, product manufacturers, and management teams. This step-by-step workflow tool will help you understand this approach effectively.

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the European Union

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02. The actors

Who's involved in the testing process?

Product manufacturer

The Product Manufacturer develops innovative building envelope technologies.

PAIN

Wants to test them in real environments before market launch.

GAIN

Gets a full report of the product performance applied to a real building, validates and improves the product.

Building Owner

The Building Owner provides physical infrastructure for testing the products.

PAIN

The building needs improvements and retrofitting

GAIN

Receives the product for free in exchange for letting the building be monitored and occupants surveyed.

03. The structure

The journey of the envelope products to be tested in the buildings

1. Matchmaking phase

2. Deployment of the Building as a Lab

3. Coordination & Installation

4. Performance evaluation

1. Matchmaking phase

This initial phase involves **identifying suitable buildings** and innovative products that align in function, purpose, and performance goals. It requires **active engagement from both product manufacturers and building owners** to assess feasibility, clarify expectations, and align on mutual interests. The **outcome is a pairing** that ensures the demonstration is relevant, technically viable, and capable of **delivering valuable data** for performance evaluation.

04. The process

Matchmaking phase

Product manufacturer

Seeks testing opportunity for their innovative envelope product

Submits a comprehensive **product application** providing product specifications, available quantities, and testing requirements

1.1

Undergoes rigorous technical screening based on **assessment criteria**

1.2

Building owner

Grants access to building infrastructure for sensor setup and data collection

Responds to **Call for Buildings** with detailed building information

1.3

Commits to the installation of the innovative technology, and actively supporting the performance monitoring phase

1.4

Established Strategic Collaboration

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1.1

Product testing application form collects key data from manufacturers, including:

- Company info & product description
- Problem addressed & proposed solution
- Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
- Innovation aspects (materials, functionality, process)
- Expected performance improvements (energy, IEQ)
- Implementation details (installation, adaptability)
- Previous test results, certifications, patents
- Market analysis & competitors
- Testing needs (quantity, parameters, timeline)

This enables initial technical screening and matchmaking with suitable Living Lab buildings.

1.2

Products are evaluated against key criteria to ensure suitability for Living Lab testing:

- Innovation Level: Novelty in technology, materials, or design
- Problem-Solution Fit: Relevance and effectiveness in addressing user/industry needs
- Technology Readiness Level: Maturity for real-world validation
- Market Potential: Commercial viability and scalability
- Competitive Advantage: Differentiators vs. existing solutions
- LL Testing Compatibility: Fit with Living Lab infrastructure and capabilities
- Environmental Impact: Contribution to energy savings, carbon reduction, and IEQ

These criteria guide selection of high-potential products for real-world testing.

1.3

Building owners participating in MEZeroE's Living Lab Testing Sites provide information about:

- Timeline for planning and installation
- Access for product setup, inspection, and monitoring
- User involvement in surveys and feedback during evaluation
- Legal requirements for permits and compliance
- Collaboration with the project manager and partners
- Agreement to outline roles and expectations
- Acknowledging the use of emerging technologies risk

This ensures successful real-world testing and performance validation.

1.4

The **compatibility assessment** confirms mutual interest and alignment between product manufacturer, building owner, and service provider. A formal agreement is signed, which formalizes stakeholder collaboration and aligns the technical and operational feasibility for deployment.

2. Deployment of the Building as a Lab

This formal step **establishes the shared responsibilities, expectations, and commitments of both stakeholders**. It includes defining the scope of product deployment, the roles of each party, data access protocols, timelines, and consent for sensor installation and occupant engagement. The **deployment agreement acts as the foundation for collaboration**, ensuring all parties are aligned legally and operationally before proceeding with physical implementation.

04. The process

Deployment Phase

Product manufacturer

Provides performance guarantees for their products solution

- ✓ Ensures **Product quality** 2.1
- ✓ Verifies **product compatibility** 2.2
- ✓ Provides a **formal commitment** establishing partnership with stakeholders 2.3

Building owner

Ensures the facility meets readiness criteria before deployment

- ✓ Provides **access to the building premises** 2.4
- ✓ Prepares building documentation and **gathers permissions** 2.5
- ✓ Ensures **optimal installation conditions** and operational collaboration 2.6

Formalized Operational Framework 2.7

2.1**Confirms product quality before deployment:**

- Verifies compliance with agreed performance standards.
- Assesses reliability and durability under expected use conditions.
- Ensures suitability for long-term monitoring in real environments.

This verifies that the product meets agreed performance standards, reliability, and durability expectations before deployment.

2.2**Validates functional, technical, and logistical suitability to ensure the technology can be deployed successfully in the Living Lab:**

- Assesses performance alignment with building goals, occupant needs, and scalability potential.
- Confirms system integration, code compliance, cybersecurity, and environmental compatibility.
- Evaluates installation logistics, delivery routes, timelines, and risk mitigation strategies.

This ensures the product's functional, technical, and logistical compatibility with the building and monitoring scope before proceeding to deployment.

2.3**Establishes a formal commitment through a Letter of Intent (LOI) that defines mutual interest and sets the foundation for collaboration:**

- Outlines the scope of technology to be tested, commitment timelines, and responsibilities of each party.
- Frames expectations around performance goals, confidentiality, intellectual property, and data ownership.
- Requires building owners to secure approvals and providers to submit documentation and project plans.

2.4**Grants preliminary approval for intervention:**

- Coordinates with planned renovations, maintenance cycles, or building improvements
- Defines approved intervention areas and scope limitations
- Establishes project timeline aligned with building operational requirements
- Obtains budget authorization for building-side costs and modifications
- Documents all approvals and authorization scope

2.5**Secures permits, internal authorizations, as well as ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements:**

- Obtains building permits for physical modifications and system changes
- Secures specialized permits for electrical and mechanical work
- Receives formal approvals from ownership and facility management
- Issues required notices to building occupants
- Verifies compliance with structural, fire safety, and accessibility codes

2.6**Ensures feasibility of installation within the building context:**

- Verifies adequate space, structural capacity, and utility availability
- Confirms delivery and installation routes through building spaces
- Validates installation and operating environmental conditions
- Assesses integration with existing building management procedures
- Plans for continued building occupancy during installation
- Develops comprehensive safety procedures for installation activities
- Establishes inspection procedures and commissioning requirements

2.7**Formalized Operational Framework**

A detailed contractual agreement is signed, detailing services, roles, responsibilities, liabilities, guarantees, costs, and consent for participation. This outcome ensures all parties are contractually committed, setting a clear and accountable framework for implementation.

3. Coordination & Installation

This stage covers the **on-site activities required to install the innovative product solution, coordination and safety compliance**. It includes coordination with facility managers, involving external installers when applicable, integrating sensors where applicable, and ensuring systems are functioning as expected. Successful implementation enables a smooth transition to the monitoring phase with minimal disruption to building operations.

04. The process

Installation & Implementation Phase

Product manufacturer

Delivers the product and offers technical support throughout the process

- ✓
3.1
Supplies **installation-ready products**
- ✓
Ensures quality control and specifications
- ✓
3.2
Provides **technical installation support**

Building owner

Prepares the site for safe and efficient installation

- ✓
3.3
Coordinates on-site activities during installation
- ✓
3.4
Ensures **site accessibility** for installer
- ✓
3.5
Guarantees **safety compliance**

Product Successful Installed and Operational 3.6

3.1**Delivers complete technology systems and components on site in line with project schedules and quality requirements:**

- Coordinates shipment schedules, verifies inventory, and inspects components for compliance.
- Manages secure storage, documentation, and chain of custody for delivered items.
- Ensures warranty tracking and quality assurance before installation begins.

Ensures packaging, delivery, and installation readiness align with project workflows and site conditions:

- Packages components according to installation sequence, handling requirements, and environmental protection.
- Groups and labels related components to simplify workflows and reduce risk of missing items.
- Verifies availability of tools, safety equipment, calibration devices, and pre-installation checks.

3.2**Provides technical guidance, documentation, and expert support to guarantee correct installation:**

- Supplies manuals, wiring diagrams, configuration guides, and troubleshooting resources.
- Offers remote and on-site technical assistance during complex phases.
- Delivers training and integration support for maintenance staff and operators.

3.3**Coordinates installation activities on site to minimize disruption and maintain building operations:**

- Aligns contractor work schedules, manages material flow, and oversees quality control.
- Provides regular progress monitoring and issue escalation procedures.
- Communicates with stakeholders and building occupants throughout the process.

Aligns scheduling between contractors, installers, and facility management to optimize resources:

- Uses critical path analysis and milestone planning to maintain progress.
- Holds coordination meetings to resolve conflicts, share resources, and adjust schedules.
- Integrates inspection and documentation checkpoints with installation milestones.

3.4**Ensures accessibility and safety are maintained during works:**

- Provides advance notice and regular updates through multiple communication channels.
- Maintains accessible routes, essential services, and accommodations for special needs.
- Clearly marks safety zones and coordinates installation timing around key occupant activities.

3.5**Guarantees safe access routes, protocols, and work zones for installation teams while protecting building occupants:**

- Conducts safety assessments of all routes and work areas before access is granted.
- Provides personal protective equipment, hazard mitigation, and emergency procedures.
- Controls access to sensitive zones to prevent unauthorized entry.

Ensures adherence to safety standards and regulatory requirements throughout installation:

- Meets OSHA, building code, and industry-specific safety standards.
- Conducts inspections, incident reporting, and performance monitoring for safety compliance.
- Develops a safety culture through training, documentation, and ongoing supervision.

3.6**Product Successful Installed and Operational**

The innovative building technology is installed on-site following the coordinated deployment plan, with full safety compliance and stakeholder support. This marks the transition from planning to real-world operation and testing of the product in an active building, ready for monitoring and performance evaluation.

4. Performance evaluation

This comprehensive monitoring phase includes the **deployment of sensors to measure thermal comfort parameters, indoor air quality, daylight, acoustics, and envelope performance**, and to **ensure uninterrupted data access** throughout the monitoring period to support the objective performance analysis. It also integrates **Post-Occupancy Evaluation (POE)** to capture occupant satisfaction, **interviews with stakeholders** to understand their expectations and to evaluate the building-product interaction and their experiences.

04. The process

Performance Evaluation and Monitoring Phase

Product manufacturer

Submits complete technical documentation for installation and evaluation

Provides product **performance characteristics** and technical specifications

4.1

Shares **relevant monitoring requirements**, and expected outcomes

4.2

Building owner

Grants access to building infrastructure for sensor setup and data collection

Grant access to building operational data and access for sensor installation and data collection

4.3

Facilitate user engagement, **occupant surveys** and **stakeholder interviews**

4.4

4.5

Validated Performance Evaluation

4.6

Feeding into the Digital Product Passport and supporting Product Certification path

4.7

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4.1**Provides detailed technical specifications and verified performance claims as the baseline for evaluation:**

- Describes product functionality, technical parameters, and integration requirements
- Defines expected outcomes in terms of energy savings, comfort improvements, and operational efficiencies
- Provides any previous test results, guarantees, and benchmark comparisons
- Establishes baselines, success criteria, and measurement protocols

4.2**Selects relevant performance study domains based on technology impacts:**

- Thermal study
- Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) study
- Daylight study
- Acoustics study
- Envelope performance
- Other requirements

Sets expected results, priorities, and thresholds for performance monitoring.

4.3**Authorizes installation of monitoring infrastructure and ensures integration with building systems:**

- Entails the building owner's responsibility to grant access for sensor installation
- Approves sensor types, specifications, and installation locations
- Reviews installation standards, security considerations, and integration procedures
- Guarantees continuous, secure, and reliable data access throughout the evaluation period

4.4**Captures occupant perspectives through structured post-occupancy surveys to validate comfort and satisfaction outcomes:**

- Indoor Environment Quality (IEQ) Feedback: User's experience of the indoor environment conditions (thermal environment, indoor air quality, ventilation, lighting, and acoustics).
- Building Context & Interaction: Details about the building, space usage, and how users interact with it.
- Participant Profile & Health Background: Information about the person responding and their well-being.

4.5**In-depth stakeholder interviews to gather operational, managerial, and experiential insights:**

- Involving facility managers, operators, tenants, and decision-makers in structured interviews.
- Documenting feedback on integration, performance, and user experience.
- Recommendations and lessons learned to inform future deployments.

4.6**Validated Performance Evaluation**

A detailed performance evaluation report is generated based on collected data, summarizing the sensor measurements and occupant feedback, providing outcomes for both product validation and further development. The report supports decision-making, future improvements, and market readiness for the innovative product.

4.7**Ensure your innovative building product meets European market standards**

The Building as a Lab service supports Digital Product Passport (DPP) population and CE Marking by delivering real-world performance data, traceable documentation, and user feedback. Data collected through installation, monitoring, and stakeholder interaction can strengthen compliance files and demonstrate lifecycle transparency, which is key for circular economy and legal placement on the EU market.

Relevant links:

- [Digital Product Passport](#)
- [CE Marking for Construction Products](#)
- [Construction Products Regulation \(CPR\)](#)
- [European Green Deal - Circular Economy](#)

05. Contact us

Want to test a product, propose your building, or replicate this process?

Want more information on how to **start this journey**?

Or just want to **share your suggestions**?

Contact us!

First name

Last name

E-mail

Organisation (optional)

Who are you?

Message

Privacy

I've read the [privacy policy](#).

Send Message

06. Download more resources

Guidelines, examples, real demo cases

Read the guidelines developed in various research projects, and discover examples of real buildings already used as open innovation test beds.

Coming soon ↓

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